

Road Safety and Capacity Evaluation of the Kashar–Vorë–Durrës Expressway Segment

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Abstract

This paper presents a detailed assessment of traffic flow along a key corridor of the Albanian road network, focusing on road safety issues along the Tirana–Vorë–Durrës axis (Kashar–Vorë–Durrës section). This corridor serves one of the country’s principal industrial regions and experiences, on average, one accident every four days. Although a declining trend is observed, the rate remains significant. Albania’s adoption of the National Road Safety Strategy, as part of its alignment with European Union requirements under candidate country status, reflects the importance of the road transport sector, which accounts for approximately 76% of total transport volume. Implementation of the Strategy’s measures has contributed to a gradual reduction in accidents; however, fatality rates remain higher than EU averages, while injury rates are comparatively lower. Originally designed to expressway standards, the corridor has become increasingly hazardous due to insufficient urban planning and uncontrolled industrial development along its length. Approximately half of its 30 km are classified as accident “black spots.” To improve safety and accommodate projected traffic volumes of up to 67,000 vehicles per day, upgrading the corridor to motorway standards is recommended, alongside short-term measures such as access control, enhanced signage, and intelligent traffic management systems. Without such intervention, the Kashar–Vorë–Durrës segment estimated to cost €130 million to upgrade may reach operational saturation by 2027.

Keywords: Road Network; Expressway; Traffic Flow; Black Spots; Pan European Transport Network.

1. Introduction

Manuscript Albania has had its third National Road Safety Strategy since 2001. Referring to the data for our country (Figure 1), it is found that the number of fatal accidents is higher than the UN average, while that of injuries is lower (Figure 2).

Aligned with European Union accession standards, the Strategy reflects the EU vision that road safety is both a right and a shared responsibility [1-4]. It outlines measures to improve road safety in Albania, aiming to achieve regional best-practice levels by drawing on European and global experience.

Through this Strategy, Albania has endorsed the European “Vision Zero” initiative, founded on four core principles:

- Human life is unique and irreplaceable; therefore, the loss of life in road accidents should not be considered acceptable.
- Transport systems should be designed to promote responsible behaviour and protect users even when errors occur.
- In the event of a crash, impact forces should remain below thresholds that cause severe injury, disability, or fatality.
- Responsibility for road safety is shared between road users and those responsible for transport infrastructure.

Figure 1. Number of fatal accidents for 2023.

Figure 2. Number of accidents with injuries for 2023.

Albania faces a significant challenge in achieving the highest levels of road safety in the region. This objective is particularly demanding amid rapid economic growth, which is expected to further increase road transport demand.

In order for this growth not to lead to an increase in the number of accidents, effective measures must be taken regarding some of the main aspects of road safety such as:

- Driver training and testing.
- Vehicle inspection for safe driving.
- Road user behavior.
- Road infrastructure safety.

The following section examines road infrastructure safety issues along the Kashar–Vorë–Durrës segment.

2. Current situation

The Based on the National Transport Plan, the important Tirana-Durres artery is connected by the Kashar Bypass, with the North-South Corridor, respectively with the construction of the Milot-Thumanë-Kashar-Rrogozhinë road.

As a result, the road system of the most important industrial region of Albania is overloaded, as the load of goods and passenger traffic is very high on some of the main roads leading to cities outside Durres and Tirana and connecting the North with the South [4] (Figure 3). It is also home to about a third of the population.

Figure 3. Map of the Transport System in the Tirana-Durrës Region.

The road corridor, which connects these two urban centers, has become a major transport artery of the country, a fact that is evidenced by the high flow of mobility and the presence of various businesses and services.

The number of businesses in the region is 81346 units [5]. This number is composed of businesses in the districts of Durrës and Tirana. At the national level, they are represented by 30% in the district of Tirana and 8% in the district of Durrës.

Figures 4 and 5 shown respectively the freight traffic flows in the Tirana-Durrës Region and passenger traffic flows in the Tirana-Durrës Region.

Figure 4. Freight traffic flows in the Tirana-Durrës Region

Figure 5. Passenger traffic flows in the Tirana-Durrës Region

From a Road Safety perspective, the Tirana-Vora-Durrës axis presents a series of problems [4, 5], which could be grouped as follows on Figure 6:

Figure 6. (a)-Entrance and exit from roadside businesses; (b)-Exiting the road and crossing onto a secondary interurban road, without signage, without a deceleration lane and with a 90° turn, a potential source of road accidents; (c)-Lack of side markers on one-way roads, up to km 8. Even after this kilometre, the markers are the wrong colour; (d)- Lack of electronic devices, visible to drivers, for controlling permitted speed limits.

As illustrated in the photographs, only one speed enforcement camera is installed, operating in a single direction, and it is currently non-functional. It is recommended that the device be upgraded with an automated mechanism for the immediate detection and recording of vehicles exceeding speed limits. In addition, a corresponding unit should be installed in the opposite direction, and two further devices positioned at Qafë Kashar and Sukth.

The Tirana–Durrës corridor was originally designed to expressway standards. However, over time, the surrounding road environment has become increasingly hazardous due to insufficient or absent urban planning, posing significant road safety risks.

The above shortcomings, but certainly not only them, have contributed to the high number of accidents on this road axis, see Figure 7.

The determination of black spots was done with a method that allows the analysis of road network elements associated with accident events over a period of time, using criteria that take into account different aspects of the data [6]. This initial assessment gave a first result: the identification of black spots, i.e., road network elements with a value, compared to a selected indicator, higher than the regional average. The distribution of "black spots" along the axis is given schematically in the Figure 8.

Figure 7. Accidents on the Tirana – Durrës road axis 2017-2024

Figure 8. The distribution of "black spots" along the axis (Tirane-Durres)

Where:

- Km 0** First pedestrian crossing
- Km 30+572** Overpassing the “Dajlan” Bridge
- 1. “Kashar”
- 2. “Gërdec”
- 3. Overpassing the “Fllakë”
- 4. “Maminas” – “Sukth”
- 5. “Yrshek”

3. Improvement Recommendations

The Kashar-Vorë-Durrës road segment is particularly busy in terms of vehicle traffic and reaches its peak in the summer period, see Figure 9. Especially with the construction of the Kashar-Milot connecting segment and further with the National Road, this load has increased significantly. As the busiest part of the region, it is also worth studying in more detail. Currently, the cross-section of this segment has the appearance as in the figure below.

Referring to European road construction standards, the maximum capacity of this road is 32,000 vehicles/24 hours. During July 2024, we carried out manual traffic measurements for 7 days in the Kashar-Vorë-Durrës segment, in both directions. Tables 1 and 2 show the manual traffic measurements made on July 23, 2024.

Figure 9. Existing condition of the Tirana – Durrës road

Table 1. Traffic measurements on the Kashar-Vorë-Durrës segment

Time		Passenger vehicles	Freight van	Minibuses	Large buses	Truck				Total
from	to					2 axes	3 axes	articular	Trailer	
7:00	8:00	1459	121	21	22	49	17	43	20	1752
8:00	9:00	1598	135	19	24	47	12	41	13	1889
9:00	10:00	1603	150	26	23	43	11	45	19	1920
10:00	11:00	1600	144	28	18	33	10	36	15	1884
11:00	12:00	1638	157	18	15	29	17	33	17	1924
12:00	13:00	1580	128	21	22	36	16	47	21	1872
13:00	14:00	1549	118	24	17	31	19	35	14	1807
14:00	15:00	1530	130	31	18	34	22	32	19	1816
15:00	16:00	1569	113	21	25	23	17	27	20	1815
16:00	17:00	1645	108	19	32	34	28	33	17	1916
17:00	18:00	1764	117	29	31	47	21	37	25	2071
18:00	19:00	1825	126	21	25	41	18	39	24	2119
Amount		19360	1547	278	272	447	208	448	224	22785
Traffic composition in %		85	6,8	1,2	1,19	1,95	0,9	1,95	1	100

Place of operation: Kashar

Date 23.07.2024

The methodology used consists of comparing the results of practical measurements with those derived theoretically with the MFD, Macroscopic Fundamental Diagram (MFD) [7], which represents the relationship between traffic flow (vehicles/hour), traffic density (vehicles/km) and average vehicle speed (km/hour).

This is a theoretical tool widely used in transport engineering and road traffic management, because it allows us to predict the number of vehicles on a road, enabling us to make appropriate decisions to avoid overloading the infrastructure.

Table 2. Traffic measurements on the Durrës-Vorë-Kashar segment

Time		Passenger vehicles	Freight van	Minibuses	Large buses	Truck				Total
from	to					2 axes	3 axes	articular	Traile	
7:00	8:00	1591	117	16	10	29	9	33	12	1817
8:00	9:00	1720	130	13	7	36	11	39	14	1970
9:00	10:00	1795	137	12	11	44	7	33	13	2052
10:00	11:00	1760	126	17	11	38	5	36	12	2005
11:00	12:00	1738	130	11	8	47	10	42	21	2007
12:00	13:00	1662	119	10	12	49	4	50	12	1918
13:00	14:00	1639	109	14	7	45	8	40	9	1871
14:00	15:00	1600	127	12	8	39	6	38	11	1841
15:00	16:00	1570	121	10	9	48	11	37	8	1814
16:00	17:00	1548	108	14	8	34	6	48	9	1775
17:00	18:00	1583	119	9	9	29	4	51	9	1813
18:00	19:00	1395	86	7	6	32	7	55	10	1598
Amount		19601	1429	145	106	470	88	502	140	22481
Traffic composition in %		87,2	6,35	0,64	0,47	2,1	0,4	2,23	0,62	100

Place of operation: Ura e Dajlanit

Date 23.07.2024

By processing the data obtained from the measurement results, we determine the average annual daily traffic [8] based on the equation (1):

$$T_{MDV} = \frac{T_{MD}}{K_S} \quad (1)$$

where:

T_{MDV} - Average annual daily traffic.

T_{MD} - Average daily traffic of vehicles circulating for 24 hours.

K_S - The seasonal coefficient, which determines the change in traffic depending on the months throughout the year. This coefficient is calculated using the equation (2):

$$K_S = \frac{T_{MDM}}{T_{MDV}} \quad (2)$$

where: T_{MDM} - Average daily monthly traffic.

This coefficient, for the Albanian Road Network, has been determined by the Institute of Transport Studies.

The table 3 depicts the seasonal coefficients for each month

Table 3: Seasonal coefficients for each month

Month	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	Oktober	November	December
Ks	0.98	0.98	1.05	1.16	0.96	1.12	1.12	1.13	0.95	0.82	0.96	1.14

The average daily traffic [9] of vehicles circulating for 24 hours is determined via equation (3):

$$T_{MD} = T_{MD_{12}} * K_{24/12} \tag{3}$$

where:

$T_{MD_{12}}$ - Average daily traffic of vehicles circulating for 12 hours from 7:00 to 19:00

$K_{24/12}$ - The report of traffic recorded for 24 hours to traffic recorded for 12 hours.

This ratio, based on automatic traffic measurements taken by the ARA, for this axis is 1.26.

Based on the measurements made and the above formulas, the average annual daily traffic and the average daily traffic are calculated for vehicles circulating on the Tirana - Vorë - Durrës road for each month (Table 4 and Figure 10).

Table 4. Average annual daily vehicle traffic and average daily traffic for each month.

Month	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	Oktober	November	December
TMDV	57035											
TMD	55894	55894	59887	66161	54753	63879	63879	64449	54185	46769	54754	65020

Figure 10. Graphical representation of the volume of vehicles circulating for each month on this axis

As can be seen from the graph, even with an accepted average growth of about 3% per year (by PKT) [10], within 2027 this road segment will present serious problems regarding traffic congestion and the resulting consequences.

Therefore, the necessity of increasing the road capacity arises. Among the known ways to increase it we mention:

- a. Increasing the width of the lanes. In practice, this is not possible since the lanes have the maximum recommended value - 3.75m.
- b. Improving the road surface and its maintenance. In fact, from this point of view, the entire Tirana - Vorë - Durrës road is one of the most assisted roads of the entire Albanian road network.
- c. Using Intelligent Transport Systems, with the benefits that have been analyzed in other works by the authors.
- d. Transition from the existing Main Interurban Road, 2x2 (for the sake of truth, this is also not in accordance with the standard - the belonging lane is missing), to the recommended next variant, 3x3 with 3.75m wide lanes, with 3m emergency lanes on both sides. So, transition to the Motorway category [11] with a maximum calculated 67,000 vehicles in 24 hours (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Tirana – Durrës Highway Proposal

The approximate cost of such an intervention would be around 130 million Euros. Both parts of this segment, the Qaf Kashar-Vorë Intersection (6 km) and Vorë-Dajlani Bridge (19 km), should be completed around 2028.

4. Conclusion

Improving safety on the Tirana–Durrës corridor requires both immediate and medium-term measures. Short-term interventions include restricting business access along the axis, removing hazardous separators, and deploying intelligent speed enforcement systems. Medium-term upgrades involve converting the existing 2×2 road into a 3×3 motorway with 3.75 m lanes and 3 m shoulders, accommodating up to 67,000 vehicles per day, while future complementary corridors are expected to redistribute traffic.

This study’s novelty lies in providing the first integrated assessment of traffic flow and road safety for this corridor, linking empirical data with staged infrastructure

recommendations. The proposed measures support regional socio-economic development, enhance environmental outcomes, and contribute to the implementation of Albania's National Road Safety Strategy.

Conflict of interests

The authors would like to confirm that there is no conflict of interests associated with this publication and there is no financial fund for this work that can affect the research outcomes.

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